

CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF IDEOLOGY IN THE NIGERIAN MEDIA: A STUDY OF SELECTED NEWSPAPER HEADLINES.

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Abstract

This study examines the ideological role of language in media discourse. It significantly reveals that news discourse is a product of the social process and that a strong connection exists between Language and ideology. Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics Model and Critical Discourse Analysis, which views Language as social semiotic and social practice, was adopted for the analysis of data. Two Nigerian newspapers, *The Nigerian Tribune and Daily Trust*, were chosen because they reported on events during the last quarter of 2022 and the first quarter of 2021, a period marked by political campaigns and the Nigerian General Elections. The study reveals that linguistic variation in the headlines of the newspaper under study is not just a function of the choice of syntactic forms, but also that they represent the paper's perception of events that have some ideological impression, especially in the Nigerian political scene. The study also concludes that news headlines are an emotion-inducing strategy in the hands of the editor used to initiate, sustain discourse, and shape the view of the readers on national issues such as politics.

Keywords: critical discourse, discourse analysis, ideology, media, Newspaper headlines

Introduction

Critical Discourse Analysis is a type of discourse that contributes to social and Cultural research by examining how language functions in specific social contexts. In this research, attention is paid to language behaviours by examining discourse texts that have occurred in particular Contexts and identifying how language use in any text reflects social identities, social relations, and Systems of Culture and beliefs. Norman Fairclough Posits that "Language is a Social practice and a part of Social processes, and as such the ideological nature of language should be one of the major concerns of social or Linguistic analysis" (133).

Central to this is that speakers make choices regarding Vocabulary and grammar, and that these choices are conscious or unconscious. "Principled and Systematic" (Roger Fowler, 21). Thus, Choices are ideologically based. He reiterated that the "relation between form and content is not arbitrary or Conventional but form-significant context" (188). Put, language is a social act, and it is ideology-driven. This approach puts particular emphasis upon "common sense assumptions" which are implicit in the conventions according to which people interact linguistically and of which people are generally not consciously aware. Such assumptions are ideologies. Ideologies are closely linked to Power because the nature of the ideological assumptions are embedded in Particular conventions and so the nature of those conventions themselves, depends on the power relation that underlies the convention; and because they are a means of legitimizing existing social relations and differences of Power, simply through the recurrence of ordinary familiar ways of behaving which take these relations and power differences for granted. (Fairclough, 45). It can be said here that Conventional practices affect the means of linguistic expressions; hence, any linguistic text carries with it an 'implicit assumption' about Social practices, and much of the interpretation of meaning and supply of some "missing link" of information is done by means of inference, since the conventions which the text reflects are taken for granted. Roger Fowler argues further that "when social norms are infringed or the Legitimacy of the institution of control is challenged, there is commonly a response in the media that tends to show most visibly the existence and effects of specific and often different ways of receiving things (118). Tony Trew in his paper, "What the paper says: linguistic variation and ideological differences", demonstrates that people and institutions especially the mass media perceive social realities differently, and this clearly finds expression in language use (10). In his words, when people talk of "not speaking the same Language even when they are speaking the English or French, the "difference" in question is about differences in thought, perception or ideology, which manifest in a Systematic and often peculiar. Configuration of linguistic items

Language in this sense has grown dramatically in terms of the uses it is required to serve, in terms of the range of language Varieties, and in terms of the

complexity of the Language capacities that are expected of the Modern citizen. Norman Fairclough (3) thus argues that "ideology is pervasively present in language"; this means the ideological nature of Language should be one of the significant means of manufacturing consent.

The mass media and Society mutually interact and influence each other. Media text, therefore, is reflective of the beliefs, biases, and interests embedded in society, and these beliefs, biases, and interests are, in turn, reinforced by media text to create a media-society nexus (Jeff Lewis 25). This approach subjects the traditional conceptualization of media objectivity to serious checks, which, as it were, tends to serve the media from their Political, Economic, and Cultural Circumstances (Ben Bagbikian 71).

In media reportage of societal issues, they inevitably project certain ideologies and power interests. Thus, the media become implicated in differences in language use and ideological stance, in this context, reflecting the process whereby media use of language generates certain ideological tendencies and promotes corresponding power interests. Thus, the literature reveals that media reportage of political institutions and events in different parts of the world is often influenced by ideological biases, which depend on factors such as ownership, political climate, and culture, and these biases naturally serve specific power interests (Fairclough and Biernazki 24).

In Nigerian democracy, Politics has become a central ideological issue, which is naturally reflected in the language of its media. Studies on news headlines have predominantly focused on the social functions of the news, structural patterns, and some speech variations in news headlines. This study set out specifically to find out how CDA, as a discourse analytical method, plays an important role in bringing out the hidden ideology in news headlines of two Nigerian newspapers and making bare the presence of power in media discourse studies with specific reference to political discourse in Nigeria. This approach is particularly significant given Nigeria's complex geopolitical structure. Again, people tend to fit into some specific pattern of behaviour as part of the Socialization process, and language has a way of reflecting this in the media.

CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS, IDEOLOGY AND MEDIA DISCOURSE

Critical Discourse Analysis

Critical discourse analysis is an offshoot of Critical linguistics (CL). Fairclough posits that "While earlier contributors in CL were comprehensive in the grammatical analysis, they paid less attention to the intertextual analysis of texts: the linguistic analysis is very much focused on clauses, with the attention to higher-level organization or whole texts" (26), Despite raising these issues with

regards to the works in CL, Fairclough maintains that "mentions of these limitations are not meant to minimize the achievement of critical linguistic.... they largely reflect shifts of focus and developments of theory in the past twenty years or so" (28), The "Shift of focus and development of theory" which Fairclough talks about, however, have not resulted in the creation of any one theoretical framework. CDA today, according to Bell & Garret "is best viewed as a shared perspective encompassing a range of approaches rather than as just one school" (7).

Among the practitioners of CDA, van Dijk is one of the most often referenced and quoted in critical Studies of media discourse, including Studies that do not necessarily fit within the CDA Perspective. In the 1980s, Van Dijk started to apply his discourse analysis theory to media, focusing mainly on the representation of ethnic groups and minorities in Europe. In his news analysis, he integrates his general theory of discourse of news in the press and applies his theory to authentic cases of news reports. He calls for a thorough analysis not only of media discourse but also for analysis and explanations of the production and "reception," or comprehension level.

Wodak Ruth dwells on the discourse historical approach. She believes that Language "manifests social processes and interaction" and "constitutes those processes as well. Wodak and Ludwig maintain that language this way entails that discourse "always involves power and ideologies" (12). That is, "no interaction exists where power relations do not prevail and where Values and norms do not have relevant roles", that "discourse is always historical, that is, it is connected. Synchronically and diachronically with other communicative events which are happening at the same time or which have happened before" (12), that readers and listeners, depending on their background knowledge and information and their position, may have different interpretations of the same communicative event (13). This way, Wodak and Ludwig assert that "THE RIGHT" interpretation does not exist; a hermeneutic approach is necessary.

The third main approach to CDA and more Central in this study is that of Norman Fairclough. In his very early works, he referred to his approach as Critical Language study. He describes this approach as "a contribution to the general raising of consciousness of exploitative social relations, through focusing upon language (4). Chouliaraki and Fairclough postulate that CDA makes a discrete contribution. They maintain that "the Past two decades or so have been a period of profound economic and social transformation on a global scale" (30). They assert that although these changes are due to particular actions by people, the Changes have been perceived as "part of nature" (4). Put, Changes and transformations have been perceived as natural and not due to People's Casual actions. According to Chouliaraki and Fairchongh (4), the recent economic and Social Changes "are to a significant degree transformation in the Language and discourse", thus CDA

can help by theorizing transformation and Creativity, an awareness of what is, how it has come to be, and what it might become or the basis of which people may be able to make and remake their lives. Fairclough further argues that "media discourse contributes to reproducing social relations of domination and exploitation (44). Thus, he maintains that "Politics of the media should be considered in media analysis as well (36).

His primary focus is on the hidden ideologies in media discourse. He summarizes various approaches to media discourse, including linguistics, Conversations, Semiotics, Social cognitive analysis, etc., and introduces his socio-cultural approach (62). In his book *Critical Discourse Analysis*, he suggests that discourse representation in news media can be seen as an ideological process and may be tuned to social determinants and social effects (Fairclough 60)

The central claim of CDA is that all human Usage encodes ideological patterns; that is, language is not just a transparent medium of Communication about the objective world, but a constantly operative part of the social process. (Malkm Kjaer. 89). CDA, therefore, analyses discourse to bring out the meaning (Sue McGregor, 115). In most interactions, users bring with them different dispositions towards language, which are closely linked to their social dispositions. Gunther Krees stresses that the "defined and delimited set of statements that constitute a discourse are themselves expressive of, and organized by a Specific ideology" (10).

Ideology in this Study is defined within the context of its relevance to language use. Ideology refers to attitudes, Sets of beliefs, values, and doctrines regarding religion and political, social, and economic life, which shape the individual and group's perception and through which reality is constructed. Rotimi Taiwo Posits that "no news report is ideologically neutral" (221). Fairclough draws upon Gramsci's definition of ideology: it refers to the conception of the world that is implicitly manifest in art, in law, in economic activity, and individual and collective life (Grami, 328). Put differently, it can be described as a set of conscious and unconscious opinions or beliefs, especially political beliefs, that characterize a Particular Culture and ideas proposed by the ruling class of society. Text can be seen as the implicit and unconscious materialization of ideologies, whose properties at various levels, such as grammar, vocabulary, metaphor, implicature, Presuppositions, and style, can be potentially ideological (Fairclough, N. 87).

Also, Iwo Olowe posits that "the editor and his reporters on the one hand, and their audience constitute an ideological empire. The newspaper subjects all newsworthy events that constantly, come up in social life to rigorous linguistic manipulation to make them suit the ideological expectations of the audience" (8). It can be said from the above that regular aspects of media Messages such as news

reports, headlines, advertisement, editorials, features, etc are "often Subject to the linguistic manipulations". This occurs as gatekeepers "work on societal Values, Conception of the world and symbolic Systems to create their message (Rotimi taiwo 221).

Media discourse in this study refers to the use of language in the mass media. It concerns mainly the interactive process that goes on between journalists and the general public. Media discourse, like any other form of language use, is a social practice, and this particular Study argues that journalists and readers are the leading actors in news discourse, rather than a social interaction among journalists (Ron Scotton 78). Media discourse takes advantage of the socio-cultural and historical relationship that exists between People and society, and the role of language in constructing this relationship in ensuring a constant social interaction. Put differently, news discourse mediates social interaction, and readers are participants in these practices.

Media discourse in this study refers explicitly to the news headlines of selected publications from the *Nigerian Tribune* and *Daily Trust* newspapers. A newspaper is an essential medium, and it is beneficial to express and deliver someone's ideas, show the power of a person, and is a valuable tool for persuasion. It can also be said that the newspaper is a source of power in society. This is evident because the words used, whether spoken or written, are never neutral; whatever people say or write always carries a hidden message, and it shows the power that reflects our interests (John Fiske 19).

Existing literature has implicated newspapers in the rise of political and ethnic consciousness in Nigeria. Daramola Ifedayo, in its detailed analysis, shows that Nigerian newspapers have, from the outset, been tied to the apron strings of their owners, and as such, have become partisan and tribal as necessitated by the respective political and ethnic affiliations of these owners. He contends that the influence of ownership and ethnic background on reportage as found in newspapers of the Colonial and early independence eras survives till today. Thus, studies on newspaper headlines and reportage on key national issues in the country tended to show that many of the reports carefully take sides on ethnic, Political, regional, or religious issues.

Newspaper headlines function as forerunners to news reports. They specifically reveal the Social, cultural, and national representations circulating in a society at any particular time. They reach a considerably wider audience than the news story. Newspaper editors go for eye-catching expressions.

Rotimi Taiwo contends that headlines are strategically used by the editor, who chooses emotive Vocabulary, rhetorical devices, and graphological elements to make an impact on the readership (32). Newspaper headlines are rich sources of information about the field of cultural reference, and they can sometimes be

challenging to understand, especially when the reader can not recognize the field, allusions, issues, and cultural references necessary to understand the content. The reader must have a good grasp of the news set, ie the reality that is assumed to be widespread in the society at that particular time, for instance, readership of newspapers especially the headline news in the last quarter of 2022 and the first quarter 2023 has been all about the Political activities from election primaries, cases after primaries, and then the electioneering campaigns followed by the General Election.

Theory/ Methodology.

Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG) is devoted to the study of the context and socio-cultural background of the discourse, thus becoming the basis of many Critical approaches and methods of discourse analysis, and plays a leading role in the Critical analysis of Public discourse. Systemic functional grammar, a functional-based approach to language study, views language as social behavior or "Semiotic". Analysis of linguistic data is based on utterances that have occurred in real Social situations. Such a study shows how language performs in different social Contexts and how meaning, social processes, and attitudes are constructed in various ways.

In characterizing the functional components of grammar, Michael Halliday (78) views language as simultaneously performing three "meta-functions". The experiential component, which is the part of grammar concerned with the expression of experience (ie, ideational function), the grammar of Personal participation; that is, establishing and sustaining relationships and social roles (interpersonal function), and the textual function, which is the creation of text. It is an enabling function connecting discourse in the co-text and the context in which it occurs.

This study focuses on experiential function. This function is represented in the chase by the participant's Process (verbal element and circumstances of transitivity show events, States, process, and their related entities.

Both Systemic functional linguistics and critical discourse analysis View language as a social construct, showing how society influences language use. They also maintain that discursive events influence the content, which in turn influences the discursive event. Both approaches emphasize the cultural and historical dimensions of meaning. This goes to buttress the point that language does not mirror an independent object World but constructs and constitutes it (Barker, Chris & Galasinski, Dariusz, I). In the analysis of data, the function of the grammar of transitivity of some selected headlines and some parts of the news report will be reviewed. The grammar of transitivity shows how the clause is used to represent actions, events, and entities. The data extracted through qualitative content analysis were presented and analyzed. They were interpreted to arrive at

the findings of the study. This helped the analyst show how ideology influences linguistic structures, which reflect the society in which they operate.

Analysis

The data comprises three pairs of news headlines which have been selected purposively for this study. Some parts of the news reports have been referred to, where necessary, for clarity. The data is selected based on the significance of the period the news in question covered, i.e., the last quarter of 2022 and the first quarter of 2023 —a Period for the Nigerian General Election. The data is drawn from two national dailies, the Nigerian Tribune and Daily Trust, published in Nigeria during this period. The grammar of transitivity (ie, part of the ideational function) of the selected news headlines was analyzed. Transitivity focuses on the verb group (the process). The system describes the whole clause and does not use labels such as 'Subject', 'verb', or an object, since 'verb' is a word class, while 'subject' is a fundamental term. Instead, different functional labels are given to participants (realized by nominal groups), Processes (realized by verbal groups), and circumstances (realized by prepositional Phrases or adverbials signifying time, place, or manner) of each process type. This brings up three basic elements to all process structures - the process itself, the Participants in the process, and the circumstances associated with the process. This study focuses on these aspects as they manifest in the newspaper headlines under examination to highlight the language variation and ideological differences in political discourse in the media.

Material Process

The newspapers' seeming stance on objectivity in the record of facts and Circumstances; communication of information used to express warnings, and explanations, Showing the relationship between things; and Showing the perception of what happened, which is helpful to construct the inner state, and ideologies and value orientation is deducible from how dynamic verbs are deployed to report the politicking and other campaign activities of Nigerian Politicians in the 2023 General Election in the media. By these are meant: Verbs that convey an image of persuasion, information, propaganda, motivation, rhetoric, and Slogans, these typically include transitive verbs such as: 'discusses', 'meets', 'tells', 'stop', 'cancels', 'declares', 'wins', 'celebrate', 'sacked. The verbs used have an implicit tendency to inform and tend also to show objectivity on the part of the media.

Headline 1

Atiku discusses economy and security with UK govt officials (*Nigerian Tribune*, Jan 11, 2023, P3).

Atiku meets UK officials on economy and security (*Daily Trust*, January 11, 2023, p. 3)

The *Tribune* headline expresses the record of facts and circumstances that transpired between Atiku and the UK government. Atiku is the agent carrying out the process of communication (discusses) with the UK govt (Participant) on the circumstances of (economy, Security)

Atiku discusses economy, Security with the UK govt. officials

The linguistic choice (discusses) explains the material Process of disclosing information or messages on the economy and security situation in Nigeria. This is with the perception of advancing solutions to these Problems. The newspaper further reports that they are "likely to be of mutual interest if he (Atiku) is elected the President of Nigeria" (*Tribune*, Ps).

Daily Trust, on the other hand, used the verb 'meets'. This highlights the process of coming together for a face-to-face arrangement. *Daily Trust*'s choice of the process function (meets) is to draw on the conceptual function of mutuality between the PDP Presidential candidate, Atiku, and UK officials.

Atiku meets UK officials on the economy and securing others.

To influence the public on the personality of PDP's Atiku, the report expresses further that "the United Kingdom (UK) invited its candidate, Atiku Abubakar, to discuss issues of common interest" (12). In the same report, Chief Dele Momadu, the director of Strategic Communications of the PDP Campaign, is quoted as saying, "Five weeks to election and the UK government invites the front leading Candidate to discuss areas of future potential Collaboration between both countries" (12). This is an ideology that puts the PDP's Atiku Abubakar in international acceptance over the other political parties' flag bearers.

Verbal Process

There is a process of communication used to convey information, such as warnings and explanations. It has to do with the symbolic relationship formed in human consciousness and presented in the form of language.

Headline 2

G5 PDP Comments: CJN is not Partisan, only joking

- Raji SAN (Nigeria *Tribune*, Nov. 23, 2022, P3) Stop hobnobbing with Politicians, Atiku tells CJN (*Daily Trust*, Nov 23, 2022).

The *Tribune* directs the source of its quote, "CJN is not Partisan, only joking," to 'Raji SAN'. The process is presented in the active voice, utilizing the verb 'is' in the third person. It is used to explain the thoughts of the 'CJN' in the circumstances of the speech event. The report. Puts 'Raji SAN' in the light as:

Reacting to the story of Justice Kayode Arimola expressing happiness that Governor Seyi Makinde of Oyo state is among the group of aggrieved PDP governors known as the G5, who met at the Banquet in Port Harcourt, Rivers state, Raji said the CJN remains non-partisan in his actions and utterances

The entire report is in the consciousness of "Raji SAN" as all relevant information is referenced to him by constantly using the process Function "said" in the body of the report. The *Tribune*, in its report, shares the ideological Position of Sympathy and defense for the CJN's actions.

The *Daily Trust* attributed the quotation "Stop hobnobbing with Politicians" to Atiku, citing additional information: "Atiku tells CJN." The Verbal Process 'tells' is used to realize the message of the headline. The process is an order from the CJN. This portends the consciousness of Power in Atiku's language. In this report, the *Daily Trust* is merely reporting the position of the PDP, unlike the *Tribune*, which is sympathetic to the CJN in their report. This gives the two newspapers different Standpoints, meanwhile reporting from the same event. The *Tribune's* report aims to explain the activities of the CJN in the event, based on information obtained from 'Raji SAN', while the *Daily Trust's* report is set to convey a warning to the CJN, as revealed through Atiku.

Mental Process

It is a process of perception, cognition, emotion, and will. Major participants in the psychological Process are the sensor and the phenomenon. This is the process of sensing and construing a quantum of change in the flow of events taking place in our consciousness (Michael Halliday, 197). Put differently, it is the awareness of our states of being and reaction to our outer experience,

Headline 3

Ayu out, Damagum in, Wike celebrates (*Nigerian Tribune*, March 28, 2023, P3)

PDP crisis: How NWC sacked Ayu despite initial resistance (*Daily Trust*, March 29, 2023, P12)

The Tribune headline expresses the mental process of perception and emotion. The mental Process "out" is a perception that the sensor (Ayu) is forcefully removed or expelled against his will. The second process celebrates the active

voice to express the emotions of the sensor (Wike). The *Tribune* reports Wike as saying that " it was worth rejoicing that God granted him Victory over those who plotted evil against him" (P.3), This indicates a powerful emotional state of relief for Wike from the Political involvement of the national chairman of the PDP, Dr Iyorchie Ayu, in the Party's Presidential primaries and (wiki) incessant Call for his removal from the position. The "in" is used adverbially to bring to the cognition that "Damagum" is elected to replace the ousted Ayu. So it also performs a mental process for the sensor, "Damagum". The ideology is to show the inner state and political value of the sensors "Ayu", "Damagum", and "Wike".

Daily Trust expresses the attitude of the sensor. (NWC) in discharging "Ayu". The mental process. "Sacked" (Passive voice) indicates that it is against Ayu's wish. The phenomenon expresses clear cognition of this:

However, *Daily Trust* reliably gathered that Ayu initially put up resistance, saying his ouster was in bad faith, before a member of the NWC persuaded him to vacate his seat (P.12).

The discourse implication here is the political tussle for Power in the opposition party, PDP, in the bid to put things right.

Conclusion

The findings of this study show that political activities in Nigeria have emerged as an important news subject for newspapers, which accounts for the frequent and prominent coverage of political reports in these news publications. This is reflected in the findings in previous studies (such as Roger Fowler 152), Rotimi Taiwo (20), Ngwu (114), Daramola (165). The decision taken by gatekeepers to report an issue frequently and prominently is ordinarily evidence of the extent to which they consider such issues important and newsworthy (Jeff Lewis 20). Such consideration in the context of this study could stem from conflicting ideas and language use; and such politically initiated, conflicting positions are attractive subjects for the media everywhere. Another possible reason for such frequent and prominent coverage is (as seen from the representation of the significant political flag bearers in the news reports) the fact that the gatekeeper considers these major political groups as legitimate and important actors in the nation's democracy, and who should be heard.

Furthermore, the study shows that newspapers, in their reports on political activities during election periods, consider the context of the nexus of political interests that influence the report. These interests constitute the ideological and power dynamics that shape the language of persuasion, propaganda, rhetoric, and slogans to influence votes. This agrees with the critical discourse analysis theory

which conceived media text as a product of culture; as a reflection of biases and interests within society; put, as a reflection of the societal dynamic of ideology and power relation (Norman Fairclough 40), Machin & Mayr 21) Most significantly the study has shown that this theoretical perspective is valid in respect of newspaper report on political discourse in Nigeria, just the same way as it has been proven to be in other climes. The findings further validate the systemic functional linguistic theory reviewed in this work, which views language as a social behavior or semiotic, and show the purpose language performs in different social contexts. How meaning, social process, and attitudes are constructed in a variety of ways. Within the foregoing theoretical context, therefore, political discourse as seen in the newspaper would be to a great extent a reflection of the dominant discourse of politics in the Nigerian media.

Works Cited

- Bagdikian Ben, *The Endless Chain*. The Media Monopoly, 1983.
- Fairclough, Norman. *Critical Discourse Analysis*. New York: Routledge. 2013
- Fairclough, Norman. *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. London: Longman, 1995.
- Fairclough, Norman. *Critical Discourse Analysis and the Marketization of Public Discourse*. *The universities, Discourse and Society*, 4(2) 133-168, 1993
- Fairclough, Norman. *Discourse and social change*. Vol 93. Cambridge: Political Preps 1992.
- Fairclough, Norman. *Language and Power*. London: Longman, 1989.
- Fairclough, Norman. *Media Discourse*. London: Arnold, 1995
- Fiske, John. *Media Matter: Everyday Culture and Political Change*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1994.
- Fowler, Roger. *Language and Control*. London: Routledge, 1979
- Gunther, Kress. "Cultural Discourse Analysis" in R. Kaplan (ed). *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*. Vol. II, 1990.
- Halliday, Michael. *Language as Social Semiotic*. London: Edirand Amolo. 1978
- Daramola, Ifedayo. "Ethnic Consideration in Political Coverage by Nigerian Media". "Kuwait chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review". Vol. 2(12), 38-52 2013.
- Jeff, Lewis. *Language Wars: The Role of Media and Culture in Global Terror and Political Violence*. London Pluto, 2005.

- Olowe, Iwo. *Language and Ideology in Nigerian Newspapers in the English Medium*. An unpublished Ph.D Thesis, O.A.U. Ile-Ife, 1993.
- Ron, Scollon. *Mediated Discourse as Social Interaction: A Study of New Discourse*. London: Longman, 1998.
- Sue, McGregor. *Critical Discourse Analysis: A Primer*. https://www.kon.org/archieves/forum/15-1_Mcgregor_cda.html. Retrieved 20:15.2022.
- Taiwo, Rotimi. "Speech as Headline in Nigerian Newspapers in The Domestication of English in Nigeria". Awoniwis. S. & Babalola, E (ed) Lagos Unity Press, 2004.
- Taiwo, Rotimi. *Language, Ideology, and Power Relations in Nigerian Newspaper Headlines*. Nebula 4(1), 218-245.2007.
- Teun, Van Dijk. *News as Discourse*. Hillside, NZ: Eribanm, 1988.
- Trew, Tony. "What the papers say: Linguistic Variation and ideological differences" in Roger Fowler (ed) *Language and control*. London: Routledge, 117-156. 1979.
- Wodak, Ruth, and Ludwig Christian. *Challenges in a Changing World: Issues in Critical Discourse Analysis*. Veria: Passagenverlag.
- Wodak, Ruth. *Power and Ideology: Studies in Political Discourse*. Amsterdam: John Beryamins, 1989.
- Wodak, Ruth. *Power and Ideology: Studies in Political Discourse*. Amsterdam: John Benjamin